

INSTRUCTIONAL PROCESSES IN A CONSTRUCTIVIST CLASSROOM FOR AN EFFECTIVE TEACHING-LEARNING OUTPUT

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ABSTRACT

Over the past decades many educators proposed different teaching strategies to meet the different needs of the learners. As mandated by RA 10533 the Department of Education issued a Regional Memorandum No. 11 Series of 2015 the office reiterates the use of the 2C-21- 1R approaches (constructivist, collaborative, inquiry -based, integrative, and reflective). These approaches were still implemented even in the existing change in teaching modality due to the pandemic. This study was conducted to determine the constructivist instructional processes and its role for an effective teaching-learning output in Alaminos district for SY 2020-2021. It aims to identify if there is significant relationship between the constructivist instructional processes and the teaching – learning output. The researcher used a quantitative descriptive and correlational approach in the study. The respondents were one hundred five elementary teachers in the District of Alaminos. The result of the study shows that the teacher respondents highly practices cognitive and social constructivism. It also discovered that the instructional performance of the teachers and the learner’s performance are very satisfactory. Moreover there is a positive significant relationship between constructivist instructional processes and the teaching-learning output as to the teacher’s performance and the learner’s performance.

Keywords: Teaching-Learning Output; Instructional Process; Cognitive constructivism; Teacher’s Performance; Learner’s Performance